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An online tool for a multicampus Master's Theses support system

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ABSTRACT

Six years ago, several higher education institutions offering study programmes in Engineering Technology underwent a thorough change, evolving from independent entities into an integrated multicampus faculty under a single governing board and a central faculty administration at KU Leuven, Belgium. Consequently, educational management structures at the new campuses were forced to adapt in order to remain functional while maximizing multicampus complementarity.

This paper describes the transformation process of the educational management support procedure for Master's Theses within the same programme at three different campuses. Under the coordination of the faculty educational developer, a new online collaboration tool was established as a portal to collect, check, select and assign Master's Theses proposals for campus coordinators, supervisors, students and industrial partners of the different campuses.

After one year of implementation, feedback from stakeholders identifies the support for sustainable and transparent collaboration as the main advantage of the new tool. Also, the transparent workflow with structured process steps within a single access point, as well as enhanced student participation were acknowledged. The future challenges for the tool, however, are to maintain its initial stimulant function for multicampus collaboration and to improve networking with local industrial partners between formerly single campus contacts.

Our results indicate how a software-tool embedded in an online platform can act as a leverage for sustained multisite cooperation, while indicating how both the use of ICT and human interaction need to be carefully balanced to establish a sustainable collaboration model.

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1 INTRODUCTION

In the year 2013, several institutions offering Master programmes in Engineering Technology in Belgium merged into the multicampus Faculty of Engineering Technology (FET), with 600 staff members and close to 6.000 students located at seven geographically dispersed campuses. Consequently, the organizational management support structures transformed from a single entity organisation towards a complex multiregional system, representing a challenge for faculty support services.

At FET, Master's Thesis projects are joint collaborations between students, research groups and/or industrial partners, designed to integrate disciplinary knowledge with academic and professional skills so that students may acquire and train several competencies within one research project. The organization, quality control, assignment to students and administrative follow-up of these projects is complex and the newly established campuses expressed the need for a new support system for Master Theses projects.

This paper describes the transformation process of the educational management support procedure for Master's Theses within the programme of (Bio)chemical Engineering Technology at three campuses at the multicampus Faculty of Engineering Technology at KU Leuven, Belgium.

2 BACKGROUND AND PREPARATION

There is little literature dedicated to educational support structures in multisite faculties [1]. Several authors, however, recommend a collaborative, faculty-driven approach facilitated by educational developers [2, 3] during the design of any new process, as well as to involve most – if not all – stakeholders [4]. In our approach, the different steps from design to implementation were carefully monitored by a faculty educational developer to ensure input from all stakeholders involved. The faculty educational developer acted as a liaison between the central Programme Committee and the local campus coordinators, project supervisors, students and industrial partners.

2.1 A new collaboration model

In the past, when campuses were independent institutions, staff members organized management systems for the collection, quality control and assignment of Master's Theses projects and optimized these for local needs. Each campus coordinator developed a system for their own student population, research groups and industrial partners, incorporating specific prerequisites for project ideas, their own choice of software and tools, and locally adapted assignment methods.

After the establishment of the multicampus faculty, each campus coordinator experienced an increased level of organizational complexity as their campus was now part of a larger entity. Colleagues from dispersed campuses were expected to function as a team, while their locally adapted management structures were not compatible with each other. As such, a centralized support system to manage project proposals in a coordinated and transparent manner was needed.

2.2 Adaptation of the software

Due to limited resources – both in time, money and available personnel – the Faculty Board decided to adopt an existing software-tool from another Faculty as a starting point. After some minor adaptations through iterative consultation rounds with the Programme Committee, the campus coordinators for Master’s Theses and the software expert of the existing software-tool, the tool was considered supportive for the most basic needs of the multicampus collaboration model.

The tool consisted of a database support system for all campuses involved, embedded in an online platform and a single access point for all stakeholders, with the following consecutive steps: 1) the collection of project proposals, 2) the quality control of project proposals, 3) the ranking of projects by students according to their preferences, and 4) the final assignation of one project per student (*Figure 1*). Student data were uploaded in the system through an automated feed from the main university framework, ensuring the most actual information of all students enrolled in the programme. All process steps were managed via an adjustable timetable by the faculty educational developer.

In the tool, three key roles are identified (campus coordinator, thesis supervisor and student (*Figure 1*), each with its own access portal, and with a specific view and rights.

Figure 1 Collaboration model for all stakeholders (simplified presentation)

All faculty staff members and students had general access to the tool with their personnel login to consult. External partners were able request login details by the campus coordinator to gain access to the tool.

2.3 Workflow and democratic involvement

To encompass all tasks involved in the new collaboration model, and ensure transparency for all stakeholders on all campuses, a detailed workflow was drawn, including detailed information on each role. The resulting model mirrored the multicampus collaboration model for educational programmes that are simultaneously implemented on more than one academic site.

The uniform implementation of the collaboration model at all three campuses was coordinated by the faculty educational developer and the Programme Committee, by determining the prerequisites for proposal submission and the deadlines for the process steps.

During the process step for students to rank proposals according to their preferences (*Figure 1*, step 3), the democratic involvement of students was ensured by the establishment of a high level of transparency during the ranking of proposals. For this, the process step was divided into two subsequent sub-steps: first, an open consultation period for students to revise all possible project proposals, followed by the submission of preferences. During the consultation period, students were allowed to consult all project proposals in detail during a significant amount of time. Meanwhile, students were stimulated to attend information sessions or to contact supervisors and industrial partners or to discuss possible partnerships with fellow students without time-pressure. After the consultation round, the submission period starts, during which all participants can rank the projects of their interest while the preferences of their fellow students are visible. Students do not have to worry about a first-come-first-serve pressure, which would undermine the democratic selection process. During submission, the tool does not register the time when students submit their choices, or the amount of times they changed their minds.

Specific care was given to the dynamic assignment system to make sure the tool assigned each student with a final project that was ranked as high as possible in the preference list of the student (*Figure 1*, step 4). Assignment was organized in consecutive rounds, alternating automated and manual assignment steps (*Figure 2*). First, all students who appeared as a single candidate for a certain project proposal with preference “1” (i.e. their first preference) were automatically assigned to the project. Second, where multiple candidates appeared for one project as their first preference, the supervisor had to choose one student and assign this student manually to the project in the tool. All candidates and supervisors involved in this manual assignment step, were notified by an automated email sent from the tool. After all preferences “1” were assigned, the allocation process continues with the preferences “2” and “3”, following the same methodology. The assignment system was completed as soon as all preferences have been processed. Students who did not receive a subject, were invited to participate in a second allocation round with the remaining project proposals.

Figure 2 Assignment system, alternating automated and manual steps

2.4 Implementation of the platform

Before implementation, adequate documentation with guidelines for each key role was developed and published through the faculty website. The website included an overview of all process steps and deadlines. The platform was launched simultaneously on all three campuses in January 2016.

3 EVALUATION

During implementation, informal contact with stakeholders was maintained, providing continuous feedback about multicampus collaboration, process management, student participation and work field interaction.

3.1 Multicampus collaboration

The tool was found to strengthen multicampus collaboration through easy access to information about research activities from other campuses. As such, academic staff got acquainted with colleagues from other campuses, which then invigorated a sustainable multicampus partnership and network.

Stakeholders also testified that, while designing the future tool architecture for multiple campuses, the mindset for multicampus collaboration was stimulated. While discussing uniformity of deadlines for all campuses, for example, openness towards future cooperation was stimulated, and spontaneous communication between stakeholders was enhanced. As such, the mere idea of a shared tool already sparked multicampus collaboration even before it was even implemented.

However, to collaborate with colleagues from distant campuses is not always easy, and certain technical issues with the software slowed down the intensification of multicampus collaboration. Not every supervisor was immediately convinced of the advantages of such multicampus schemes and more time may be needed for this to grow.

3.2 Process management

The tool provided a standardized workflow with clear process steps, during which each stakeholder was aware of tasks and responsibilities. The tool was considered the backbone of a complex process involving multiple stakeholders at multiple locations.

The main advantage of the tool was that it collected all proposals within one platform, monitoring stakeholder accessibility through time slots that were opened and closed according to a predetermined and transparent timeline. This helped to perform the necessary tasks in an efficient way throughout the process. As a side-effect, it was possible to divide the work load among stakeholders, as the tool provided a clear view of the tasks that needed to be done.

Within this structured approach, the use of the tool remained flexible. As the campus coordinator had unlimited access to all tool functions during all process steps, this allowed him to overrule certain tool functionalities in function of occurring needs. Taking into account the necessary precautions and quality measurements, as was expected from all campus coordinators, this prevented the software-tool to dominate over interpersonal contact and ad hoc cooperation between stakeholders.

3.3 Student participation

During the selection period, the tool allowed students to see preferences of their fellow students, which enabled them to weigh their options and to manage their preference ranking of subjects. All students were allowed to edit their ranking as many times as needed as the tool did not register input time, nor the number of changes made. However, further investigation will be needed to measure the effect of this transparent student participation in comparison with other procedures.

In the approval and publication period, students were allowed sufficient time to contact thesis supervisors and external partners, without being pressed to decide quickly. In this, the tool created calmness in a process that may otherwise be quite stressful for students, and stimulated students to obtain a project they are truly interested in.

3.4 Work field interaction

At the early stage of implementation, the effect of the tool on work field interaction was still rather uncertain, as not many external partners were informed about the new platform. However, it seems to be a rather promising aspect, as it could provide industrial partners and research groups with access to the entire student population of the Faculty through one single platform. More efforts may be needed to promote the platform among industrial partners. On the other hand, external partners may feel reluctant to work with supervisors from campuses they are not familiar with or they may want to select candidates themselves instead of through a tool. These aspects remain to be investigated in order to evaluate the possible impact of the tool on work field interaction.

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

A multicampus collaboration platform for Master's Theses was successfully designed and implemented for staff members and students in (Bio)chemical Engineering Technology at three campuses at KU Leuven, Belgium. The main advantage of this platform is its support for sustainable and transparent collaboration between all stakeholders involved in the procedure, including campus coordinators, thesis supervisors, students, industrial partners and research groups. The platform provides

transparent procedures and a single login portal, creating easy accessibility and compatibility.

The results show how the implementation of a software-tool embedded in an online platform provides organizational support in a complex multicampus process, and how such a tool can act as a leverage for sustained multisite cooperation. The future challenge for this platform will be to maintain this leverage function, and to keep up the necessary investment of human resources in order to enable its effective use for students, academic staff and external partners. After the first year of implementation, the multicampus collaboration platform for Master's Theses has already been adopted within other Master's programmes within the Faculty and currently, its model is being analyzed for broader implementation within other Faculties of the university.

The observations documented in this paper confirm that the use of ICT can enable more effective use of resources, and provide wider exposure to students and teaching staff [6, 7]. At the same time, the preliminary results in this paper identify the complementarity of ICT and human interaction and the need to balance both to establish a sustainable collaboration platform. As documented in literature, the role of the educational developer during all process steps, functioning alternately as a facilitator, change manager and coordinator [5], enabled the necessary organizational support to strengthen transparency, the technological support to help multicampus collaboration, and the quality assurance to optimize data management.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Srivastava, P (2012), Educational Informatics: An Era in Education, International Conference on Technology Enhanced Education (ICTEE).
- [2] Christensen, HJ (2007), Supporting Curriculum Assessment and Development: Implications for the Faculty Role and Institutional Support, *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, No. 112, pp. 107-110.
- [3] Wolf, P (2007), A Model for Facilitating Curriculum Development in Higher Education: a Faculty-driven, Data-informed, and Educational Developer-supported Approach, *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, No. 112, pp. 15-20.

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- [4] Hammerschmidt, P, Murphy, A, Youatt, J, Sawyer, C and Andrews S (1994), Evaluating curriculum effectiveness by asking the users, *Journal of extension*, Vol. 32, No. 3, pp. 21-25.
- [5] Van der Hoeven, W, Peeters, C, Buelens, H, Buijs, J, De Cock, M, Heylen, C, Janssens, A, Londers, E, Moyson, E and Smet M (2013), Stap voor stap naar een optimale begeleiding van projectonderwijs: praktische gids bij het gebruik van een begeleidersmodel voor wetenschappelijk en technologisch onderwijs, Faculteit Bio-ingenieurswetenschappen, KU Leuven.
- [6] Gaskell, C and Hayton E (2015), Distance administration. Multiple perspectives on multi-site institutions, *Perspectives : Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, Vol. 120, No. 6, pp. 1718-1731.
- [7] Ferron, M, Massa, P and Odella, F (2011), Analyzing collaborative networks emerging in Enterprise 2.0: the Taolin Platform, *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Vol. 10, pp. 68-78.